

Parametric bootstrapping for OU models

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In this tutorial, we demonstrate options for testing the statistical robustness of your dataset for analyzing the Hansen model. We expect readers to use this tutorial as a companion to our previous tutorial (“OU process for modeling adaptive evolution”) and our published paper (Moen *et al.* In review).

As in the previous tutorial, we will analyze evolution of CT_{\min} in hylid frogs of Middle America. We first demonstrate how to use parametric bootstrapping to calculate 95% confidence intervals. We then use the same procedure to examine the statistical properties of our data for model comparison. More generally, parametric bootstrapping means using parameter estimates from your data to simulate new datasets, then conducting similar analyses as you did on your original dataset. This type of bootstrapping allows you to incorporate uncertainty in the process (e.g. Brownian motion, OU) you are inferring for your data.

Loading data and packages

We first load all necessary R packages and data for this tutorial. We also load a .R file that contains two custom functions used in the tutorial. You can open those files separately for additional details on the functions, such as arguments and output. Note that we developed this tutorial with R version 4.0.2. It may not work well on previous versions of R.

```
library(OUwie) # Our principal package for OU analysis. Version 2.6.
library(ouch) # An alternative package for OU analysis. Version 2.17.
library(pmc) # For simple parametric bootstrapping with ouch. Version 1.0.4.
library(parallel) # For parallel analyses. Version 4.1.0.
library(phytools) # Used here for stochastic mapping. Version 0.7-70.
library(tidyverse) # Suite of packages for data manipulation. Key included packages for
# this tutorial are dplyr, tidyr, ggplot2, and purrr. Version
# 1.3.0.
source("AppendixS6_tutorial_functions.R") # Custom functions we wrote for this tutorial
load("AppendixS11_OU_bootstrap_data.RData") # R workspace with objects from previous
# tutorial
```

Calculating 95% confidence intervals (CIs)

In the previous tutorial we covered calculation of standard errors for *OUwie* model fits. Here we use an alternative method for calculating parameter uncertainty, based on parametric bootstrapping. With this method you simulate new data along your phylogeny for the characters of your interest (e.g. CT_{\min}), using the maximum-likelihood parameter estimates from your model fit for those characters. You then calculate new parameter estimates from the simulated data. After doing this many times, you examine the distribution of parameter estimates. The process of evolution you infer for your data has inherent stochasticity, so the simulation captures that randomness when estimating uncertainty in parameter estimates.

Both *OUwie* and *ouch* have functions for parametric bootstrapping of parameters. 95% CIs can then be easily calculated from the parameter distributions that result from these functions. We will start with *OUwie*. Normally we would recommend at least 1,000 replicates, but we will analyze 100 here for computational efficiency to help you move through the tutorial. We encourage readers to examine how increasing the number of simulations affects the distribution of results. Note that we want to ensure our bootstrap analyses have the same settings as our original analysis, so that results are comparable. Thus we use the fitted model object `OU2_OUwie` to specify nearly all analysis options.

```
mod <- OU2_OUwie # Changing the name simplifies later code.
set.seed(1978) # To ensure your results are identical to ours
nsims <- 100
CTmin_boot_OUwie <- OUwie.boot(phy = tree_ou2, data = dat_OU2, model = mod$model,
  nboot = nsims, alpha = mod$solution[1, ], sigma.sq = mod$solution[2,
  ], theta = mod$theta[, 1], theta0 = mod$theta[2, 1], scaleHeight = mod$scaleHeight,
  root.station = mod$root.station, get.root.theta = mod$get.root.theta,
  mserr = "known", algorithm = mod$algorithm, warn = FALSE)
```

After running the bootstrap analyses, you can extract the bounds of the 95% CI:

```
# Calculate 95% CI
apply(CTmin_boot_OUwie, 2, quantile, probs = c(0.025, 0.975))
```

```
##      alpha_temperate alpha_tropical sigma.sq_temperate sigma.sq_tropical
## 2.5%      0.7151569      0.7151569      1.111084      1.111084
## 97.5%     99.9741235     99.9741235     98.928915     98.928915
##      theta_temperate theta_tropical
## 2.5%      -3.356062      5.568976
## 97.5%      3.264791      7.549446
```

It may be worth using these bootstrap results to intuitively show the dependency between α and σ^2 that we outline in our paper's discussion. In brief, the stationary variance of the OU process depends on the ratio of these two parameters (i.e. $V = \sigma^2/2\alpha$), so it is common to find that many combinations of them can have a similar likelihood. A plot of our values estimated across bootstrap replicates shows this nicely (Fig. 1). We show code for this figure, as it uses a specific package (*ggplot2*) that is very flexible but coding can be a bit more complex than for the figures of our other tutorial.

```
class(CTmin_boot_OUwie) <- 'matrix'
CTmin_boot_OUwie %>%
  as_tibble() %>%
  ggplot(aes(alpha_temperate, sigma.sq_temperate)) +
  geom_point(size = 3, alpha = 0.7) +
  geom_abline(aes(slope = 1, intercept = 0)) +
  scale_x_log10(name = quote(alpha)) +
  scale_y_log10(name = quote(sigma^2)) +
  theme_linedraw() +
  coord_fixed()
```


Figure 1: Plot of α and σ^2 estimated across parametric bootstrap replicates. Note that we only use this plot for heuristic reasons; the simulated data are all different, so technically this is **not** showing how similar likelihoods for a given dataset can be obtained at different values of α and σ^2 . However, it should be very similar to what we want, given that all the simulations were based on the same parameter values. Both axes are in original units on a logged scale, as their variation seems to fit a lognormal distribution. The line has an intercept of 0 and slope of 1.0 to show that as one parameter goes up, the other is estimated similarly higher. Also note that some of our replicates hit the upper bound of 100 in *OUwie* for these two parameters, so this upper bound may be worth increasing in future analyses.

Now let's do the same thing with *ouch*. As in *OUwie*, you use your original model fit as an argument in a dedicated function for parametric bootstrapping. This time, the coding is a little more direct (if less flexible). *ouch* also runs much faster.

```
CTmin_boot_ouch <- bootstrap(OU2_ouch, nboot = nsims, seed = 1978)
apply(CTmin_boot_ouch, 2, quantile, probs = c(0.025, 0.975))
```

```
##           alpha sigma.squared optima.CTmin.temperate optima.CTmin.tropical
## 2.5%    0.5957301   0.9797856                -3.936317                4.903817
## 97.5%  30.3947875  85.5157044                 3.390638                 8.524398
##           loglik      aic      aic.c      sic dof
## 2.5%   -21.326521  26.26235  32.92901  27.85393  4
## 97.5%   -9.131174  50.65304  57.31971  52.24462  4
```

With both *OUwie* and *ouch*, we see that both α and σ^2 vary widely, but our optima (θ_i) have mutually exclusive 95% CIs. This makes sense, as the optima are usually much more reliably estimated than the rate parameters (see our discussion, as well as the previous tutorial, for more details). Thus, the major signal favoring OU2 as a model for our data is that temperate and tropical lineages tend to have different CT_{\min} values, and thus adaptive optima.

Parametric bootstrapping to test model support

We next use the very same parametric bootstrapping that we used for calculating 95% CIs. Now, however, we choose two models to compare, usually the model favored by AIC and either a simpler or more complex model. We simulate data twice, one for each model we are comparing. Then, for each simulated dataset, we fit

both models. The idea is to examine model-comparison results when the data are simulated under one model versus the other. In total, this makes two trait simulations (fast) and four total model fits (much slower) per simulation replicate, meaning about four times the computational effort compared to our previous use (though ultimately, computation time depends on the models that are compared). For additional description of this procedure, you can read our paper’s online Supplementary Materials and Methods. Better yet, we refer readers to Boettiger *et al.* (2012), who describe all details of the approach.

Boettiger *et al.* (2012) developed the R package *pmc* (for **Phylogenetic Monte Carlo**) to carry out model comparisons with parametric bootstrapping. Their implementation of the Hansen model uses *ouch*. However, no analogous function or package does this with *OUwie*, so we have written a function analogous to `pmc()` to simplify use. Our function is called `paraboot_OUwie()` and we demonstrate its use here. The package *pmc* has details on how to use it if you implement your OU analyses in *ouch*.

Our function has similar arguments as the base function `OUwie()`, with a list of two phylogenies and data (e.g. if they have different regimes). Most other arguments are relatively straightforward, with two exceptions. First, the argument `OUwie_args` allows you to specify any non-default settings for running `OUwie()` on your simulated datasets. In our case, we will generally use the same settings as our main analyses in our paper. Second, you can specify how many processors you would like to use for your analyses with the argument `ncores`. If you leave it `NULL`, the function will automatically estimate how many processors your computer (or computing node) has, then use all of them with the package *parallel*. Alternatively, you can specify the number of parallel analyses you want to run by specifying a number for `ncores`. This can include just `ncores = 1` if you do not want to run parallel analyses at all.

```
nsims <- 100
OUwie_args <- list(scaleHeight = T, root.station = TRUE, algorithm = "invert",
  diagn = F, quiet = T, warn = F)

# (a) Compare BM (second-most supported model) to OU2 (most
# supported model)
BMvOU2 <- paraboot_OUwie(trees = list(tree_ou2, tree_ou2), dat_list = list(dat_OU2,
  dat_OU2), mods = c("BM1", "OUM"), nsim = nsims, seed = 1978, OUwie_args = OUwie_args,
  ncores = NULL)

# (b) Compare OU2 (most supported model) to OU3 (more complex
# model)
ou2v3 <- paraboot_OUwie(trees = list(tree_ou2, tree_ou3), dat_list = list(dat_OU2,
  dat_OU3), mods = c("OUM", "OUM"), nsim = nsims, seed = 1978, OUwie_args = OUwie_args,
  ncores = NULL)
```

Let’s now examine the output. We first combine the results from the two different types of model fits. For each simulated trait, we fit both models and plot the distribution of likelihood-ratio test statistics (LR-stat) across simulation replicates. We then ask whether these distributions are distinct, which will give us a sense for how much information exists in our dataset to distinguish models. Low overlap indicates high power to distinguish. Fig. 2 shows us that we can be confident in our results for OU2 vs. BM (i.e. red line squarely within the light-grey distribution), though not as much for OU2 vs. OU3 (overlapping distributions, with the red line within both).

```
results <- bind_rows(data.frame(comparison = "BMvOU2",
  null = BMvOU2$LR_sim[,1],
  test = BMvOU2$LR_sim[,2],
  lr = BMvOU2$LR_emp,
  sig = BMvOU2$LR_sig),
  data.frame(comparison = "ou2v3",
  null = ou2v3$LR_sim[,1],
  test = ou2v3$LR_sim[,2],
```

```

lr = ou2v3$LR_emp,
sig = ou2v3$LR_sig)) %>%
pivot_longer(c(null, test), names_to = 'test_type', values_to = 'LR_ratio')

# Using the flexibility of ggplot2 you can customize the plot to visualize your observed
# test comparison ('results$lr', red lines) to what you would expect for a comparison when
# the data are simulated under the two models
ggplot(results, aes(LR_ratio, fill = test_type)) +
  geom_density(alpha = 0.75) +
  geom_vline(aes(xintercept = lr), color = 'red', linetype = 'solid') +
  geom_vline(aes(xintercept = sig), color = 'black', linetype = 'dashed') +
  scale_fill_manual(values = c('grey60', 'black')) +
  scale_y_continuous(name = 'Density', expand = c(0,0)) +
  scale_x_continuous(name = 'Likelihood ratio', expand = c(0,0)) +
  theme_classic() +
  theme(
    axis.text = element_text(color = 'black'),
    strip.text = element_text(size = 14, hjust = 0.5, vjust = 2, face = 'bold'),
    strip.background = element_blank()
  ) +
  facet_wrap(~comparison, nrow = 1, scales = 'free')

```


Figure 2: Results of parametric bootstrapping with *OUwie*. “null” distributions indicate likelihood ratios calculated between the two models when data were simulated under the simpler model. “test” distributions indicate the same, but when data were simulated under the more complex model. The darkest grey color indicates areas of overlap. Dashed vertical lines indicate the critical value for a standard hypothesis test (i.e. critical level of 0.05). Vertical solid red lines indicate the empirical likelihood-ratio test statistic.

The expected null distribution for likelihood ratios of nested models is a χ^2 distribution with degrees of freedom equal to the difference in number of estimated parameters between the models. Thus, we can next compare our distributions to a χ^2 value at a significance level of 0.05 and with the appropriate degrees of freedom. You would normally compare the empirical LR-stats (i.e. those from your data) to this χ^2 value to test whether to reject the simpler model. Thus, we can ask: when simulating data under the simpler model and comparing the model fits (light gray distributions in Fig. 2), what proportion of simulation replicates produce an LR-stat equal to or great than the χ^2 value? This is the Type-I error rate. We see that when

comparing BM to OU2, we have a low error rate (Type-I error = 0.03). It is much higher when comparing the two OU models (Type-I error = 0.34)

Alternatively, when simulating under the more complex model, we would expect to reject the incorrect simpler model. Thus, we can ask: what proportion of ‘test’ replicates return a LR-stat that is greater than the χ^2 value (dark gray distributions in Fig. 2)? This is the power to correctly reject the simpler model. We see that in the comparison of BM vs. OU2, we have a powerful test, with power = 1. Comparing the two OU models is a weaker test (power = 0.61)

References

Boettiger, C., G. Coop, and P. Ralph. 2012. Is your phylogeny informative? Measuring the power of comparative methods. *Evolution* 66:2240–2251.